

Synthesis and Characterization of Nanocomposite in Medical Application

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Abstract

There are several ways to prepare nanomaterials, including physical methods, biological methods, and chemical methods. In this research, a biological method was used to prepare silver nanoparticles using mint leaf extract, and nano-lead using cumin seed extract. Plant extracts are considered reducing agents, and the green synthesis method was used because this method is environmentally friendly, uncomplicated, and less expensive. Mint and cumin leaves were collected, dried, and then ground in a grinder. After that, the plant extract was prepared. Used 0.2g from $AgNO_3$ in 100 ml from distill water and also used 0.2g from $PbNO_3$ in 100 ml from distill water. The nanocomposites were prepared using the droplet method and were sent for examination to conduct the (XRD, FE-SEM, and UV) test on the samples. The results of the tests showed that we had obtained nanoparticles of silver and lead nanoparticles. The UV test showed peaks indicating the presence of silver inside the sample and lead inside the other sample. Absorption, transmittance and energy gap testing were also performed. The results of the XRD test also showed that the grain size of the silver nanoparticles (19.6 nm) and that its crystal structure is of (cubic) type also showed that the grain size of the lead nanoparticles range between (16.6 nm_17.4nm) and that its crystal structure is of (cubic) type. The FE-Sem examination was conducted to determine the shape and morphological characteristics of the nanoparticles, and it was used to determine the particle size of the nanocomposites. The nanosize of the silver particles ranged from 46-82 nanometers, and the nanosize of the lead particles ranged from 99138 nanometers. The resulting solutions were applied to the taken bacteria. From the eye (*Pseudomonas lutea*) and the extracts proved effective in killing bacteria. Cumin extract with lead nitrate was more effective than silver nitrate with mint extract.

Keywords: *Synthesis, $AgNO_3$, nanocomposite, medical application.*

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Introduction

The origin of the word "Nano" is derived from the Greek (Nanos), which means dwarf and means everything that is small (Jawd, Hamza, & Mahdi, n.a.).

Nanoscience is concerned with the study of the basic principles for the formation, synthesis and application of molecules and compounds whose

size measurement does not exceed 100 nm. Since the nanometer is a SI unit of measurement and is equal to 10^{-9} meters. The principle of this technique is based on capturing nanoparticles of the material, manipulating and moving them from their original positions to other positions and then combining them with atoms of other materials to form a crystal lattice to obtain materials with distinct nanoscale dimensions and

high performance and desirable properties (Wilson, et al., 2002).

Nanotechnology has attracted great attention, as this technology is one of the new technologies that still needs a lot of research and studies that have become of great importance due to their unique properties and the breadth of their applications. Nanotechnology, as stated in many nanotechnology research centers, is the technology of the next age, i.e. we can call our next age the "Nano age". This great field will be in many areas of industrial, agricultural and medical life, in the areas of transportation and aviation, in space and water technology, and in many important vital fields. At the end of the twentieth century, the world experienced a rapid development of technological science, after the invention of computers, which led to an electronic revolution, which made the competition between industrialized countries great (Kim, et al., 2018).

The invention of the microscope contributed to the penetration into the small worlds of matter, which became clearer, and man was able to go deeper into those worlds from the living worlds, including living organisms and their components, and from the inanimate worlds, including the elements of matter and its components of atoms and molecules (Wilson, 1997).

Nanotechnology is one of the most important technologies in multiple fields, as it is based on the synthesis of nanoparticles (NPs). Where these particles have different properties from the metals from which they were formed, based on the engineering of metal particles in various shapes and sizes, interest has increased in recent years in the production of metal materials. Nanoparticles have applications in various fields such as biomedical, agricultural, environmental and industrial fields. Bio-preparation of nanoparticles (biosynthesis) is carried out using metabolites or plant extracts and one of the advantages of this method is that it is environmentally friendly, does not need energy, cheap and fast (Hano, & Abbasi, 2021).

In our research, we will conduct the green synthesis process using two basic elements in nature, silver and lead and study the inhibition

zone of the *Pseudomonas luteola*. Silver is an element symbolized by the letters "Ag", an abbreviation of the Latin word (Argentum) and attributed to the country of Argentina (the land of silver), where silver was found in large quantities. It is a white metal and can be polished and refined. The silver metal comes in transition group II of the periodic table, and its number is atomic weight is 47, its atomic weight is 107,868, and its specific gravity is 10.5. Silver melts at a temperature of 962 degrees Celsius, and reaches the boiling stage at a temperature of 2212 degrees Celsius (Al-Bashir, 2015).

Lead is a chemical element with symbol Pb and atomic number 82; It is located in the periodic table within the carbon group (the 2 fourteenth group; it is also the fourth group according to the numbering of the main groups). Lead is a heavy metal with a high density, and is normally found in a bluish-silver color, which quickly loses its luster to an opaque gray color when exposed to air. Particular, lead oxide electronic properties, i.e., bandgap and hence color, depend largely on the lead to oxygen ratios and crystal structures of various polymorphs (Akimov, Gubin, & Yurkov, 2012).

Pseudomonas luteola, characterized by its distinctive yellow pigment, is a gram-negative, motile, and strictly aerobic rod. Differentiating from other yellow-pigmented non-fermenters due to its negative oxidase reaction, *P. luteola* is primarily found in environments with high moisture content (Ahmad, Alzahrani, & Alsaed, 2023). This study aims at the synthesis of silver (Ag) NPs and studying the effect of silver nanoparticles on (*Pseudomonas luteola*) bacteria. Synthesis of lead (Pb) NPs and studying the effect of lead nanoparticles on (*Pseudomonas luteola*) bacteria.

Materials and Methods

Method of Work

Preparation of the plant extract (mint)

Preparing the plant extracts. Fresh leaves were collected from the leaves of the mint plant, *Mentha spicata*, on September 6, 2023, from the city of Khalidiya. After that, the leaves were washed several times with sterile distilled, deionized water, and then they were spread in a strainer away from sunlight and at room

temperature. It was spread on dry paper and stirred several times to prevent it from rotting for a week, then it was crushed using a grinder

to obtain a fine powder of mint leaves (Al Dulaimi, 2022).

Figure 1. A- Fresh Mint, B- Ground Mint

Preparation of the plant extract(cumin)

The seeds of *Cuminum cyminum* seeds were purchased from the local market (herbs and aromatic Abu zaydoun) in the latifiya area of Al-Salam neighborhood and washed several times by water to remove dust particles and then they

were introduced to the incubator for 24 hours at a temperature of 37 °C and after taking them out of the incubator, spread them in a place to remove the remaining moisture from them and then grind them to form a powder (Joglekar, Karanjkar, & Bodas, 2011).

Figure 2. A- Dried Cumin after Leaving the Incubator, B- Ground Cumin

Extraction of Plant Extract

Prepare mint extract method

The baker, thermometer, and gauze were used, and the baker were washed well with distilled water before starting the process of preparing

the extract for the mint plants. Then 18 grams of mint and 300 ml of distilled water were used at a temperature of 42-50 °C for 35 minutes. The distilled water was mixed with the mint until it became liquid and then it was placed in the refrigerator for 24 hours.

After 24 hours had passed, we filtered the extract of mint several times through gauze to obtain the best quality of the extract. Then we used tubes to put the extract in it, so that each tube contained 10 ml of extract for each of mint, and

then we performed the centrifugation process for the extract of mint. The mint extract was centrifuged for 20 minutes at a speed of 3500 rpm (Bandar, & Ahmed, 2023).

Figure 3. A- Prepare Mint Leaves before Centrifugation. B- Mint Leaf Extract after Centrifugation. C- Place the Plant Extract inside the Tubes

Cumin extract method

The seed extract was prepared by mixing 64.32 grams of cumin and 300 ml of distilled water in a conical flask on a Stirling heating device for 35 minutes at a temperature of 35-40 °C. To improve the mixing process, we close the mouth of the conical flask, then put the solution in the tripod for 24 hours, and after 24 hours have passed, we filtered the cumin extract several

times through cheesecloth to obtain the best quality of the extract.

Then we used tubes to put the extract in, so that each tube contained 10 ml of cumin extract. Then we performed a centrifugation process for 20 minutes at a speed of 3500 rpm, then separated the supernatant, filtered it using a filter (filter paper), and took the solution (Bandar, & Alani, 2023).

Figure 4. A- Prepare Cumin. B- Prepare the Cumin before Centrifugation, C- Place the Cumin Extract into the Tubes

Methods Prepare Silver and Lead Nitrate

Methods prepare silver nitrate

Silver nitrate should be prepared in a dark place away from light. Silver nitrate was prepared in light-insulating glass and covered with aluminum foil. Where (0.2 g) of silver nitrate was added to (100 ml) of deionized water (El-Din, n.d.).

Methods prepare lead nitrate

Lead nitrate should be prepared in a dark place away from light. Lead nitrate was prepared in light-insulating glass and covered with aluminum foil. Where (0.2 g) of lead nitrate was added to (100 ml) of deionized water (Bandar, & Alani, 2023).

Method Load Mint Extract onto Silver Nitrate

We took 15 ml of mint leaf extract and took 10 ml of diluted silver nitrate.

Figure 5. Mint Extract with Silver Nitrate during the Calibration Process

The temperature of the thermometer was measured using a pre-set between (6070) °C as a specific range. After that, the silver nitrate was added in a dark container, the extract was added in a numbered buret, and the container containing the 10 ml of silver nitrate was placed on the thermometer. The burette containing the extract was placed over the nitrate container

placed on the thermometer. The extract from the burette was added to the container by a drop method, and when the mixture turned to the desired color of bronth black, the process, which took 25 minutes was stopped.

Method Load Cumin Extract on Lead Nitrate

20 ml of cumin extract was taken, 10 ml of diluted lead nitrate was taken, and the thermometer was set at 40 °C, and using the dripping method with a burette for 25 minutes, and we got a color close to dark orange (Vigneswari, et al., 2021).

Figure 6. Cumin Extract with Lead Nitrate during the Calibration Process

Prepare the Sample to XRD and UV Tests

A small amount of silver nitrate AgNO_3 was placed with mint extract that had been previously prepared by distillation on a slide on the thermometer, and then the sample was waited until it dried. After that, the sample was removed from the thermometer and placed in a dish, and the address of each sample was then placed. The examination was repeated with lead nitrate and cumin extract, and it was prepared for the purpose of XRD examination. Also put the liquid Frome AgNO_3 + plant extract 5ml in

tube. PbNO₃ with plant extract 5ml in tube to UV test.

Results and Discussion

UV Ultraviolet Spectrum Results (Absorption, Transmission and Energy Gab)

UV Ultraviolet spectrum results(absorption)

UV-visible absorption spectrum of Ag and Pb nanoparticles within the wavelengths (200-1100) nm. The absorption of pb appears at a

wavelength of 430 nm is 0.32 λ Consistent with previously published research Uzair, et al. (2020), which showed that the wavelength is approximately 420 nm. As for the second compound Ag the appears at a wavelength of 450nm is 0.17 λ Consistent with previously published research Jadoun, et al. (2021), which showed that the wavelength is approximately 460 nm and that mean the absorption of PbNO₃ with cumin extract large than AgNO₃ with leaf mint extract.

Figure 7. Absorption of Nanomaterials for Silver and Lead

UV Ultraviolet spectrum results (transmission)

UV-visible transmittance spectrum of Ag and Pb nanoparticles within the wavelengths (200-1100) nm. The transmittance of Ag appears at a

wavelength of 340nm at a rate of 95%. As for the second compound pb the transmittance appears clearly at a wavelength of 400nm at a rate of 80%. And that mean the transmission of pbNO₃ with cumin extract less than AgNO₃ with leaf mint extract.

Figure 8. Transmittance of Nanomaterials for Silver and Lead

UV Ultraviolet spectrum results (Energy gab)

In our previous research on the green synthesis of silver nanoparticles, with a prominent source of research Salleh, et al. (2020) the distinguished calculation for silver was calculated, which shows 3.4ev, but the energy importance of silver in our research was 2.1ev, and there is a difference between the energy values of the gaps of the previous research and our current

research, due to the oxidation of our silver element. The reason is due to the picker lens containing 25% silver nitrate.

In previous research on nano-lead, which dealt with the study of the semiconducting behavior of nano-lead, which comes from Noureen, & Ashraf, (2023) the energy gap of lead was calculated, which was valued at 2.46ev, and its value was close to the value obtained in our research, which was 2.3ev.

Figure 9. Energy Gab of Nanomaterials for Silver and Lead

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) of (lead and silver)

X-ray Diffraction (XRD) of lead

The test results showed that the powder used is nano lead. The results of the XRD test also showed that the grain size of the lead nanoparticles ranges between (16.617.4) nm and that its crystal structure is of (Cubic) type as shown in the figure (19) and table (4.2). The particle size of lead was calculated using the equation (2-2).

The specific XRD pattern of lead nanoparticles show the presence of lead with peaks at 31.58,36.58 which confirm the presence of lead in the sample. Consistent with published research (Garry, & O'Reilly, 2020).

$$D_{Khl} = K\lambda / (B_{khl} \cos\theta) \quad (1)$$

Table 1. X-Ray Parameters of the Prepared Pb Nano Particles

2θ (Deg.)	FWHM (Deg.)	d _{hkl} Exp.(Å)	C.S (nm)	Hkl	Phase	card No.
31.5885	0.4732	2.8301	17.4	(111)	Pb	96-901-3419
36.5864	0.5027	2.4541	16.6	(200)	Pb	96-901-3419

Figure 1.: X-Ray Diffraction Pattern of the Prepared Pb Nano Particles

X-ray Diffraction (XRD) of silver

The test results showed that the powder used is nano silver oxide. The results of the XRD test also showed that the grain size of the silver oxide nanoparticles (19.6 nm) and that its crystal structure is of (Cubic) type as shown in the figure (20) and table (4.2). The particle size of lead was calculated using the equation (2-2).

X-ray diffraction of silver oxide nanoparticles shows the presence of silver oxide with peaks of 32.3 corresponding to the following publication (Parrey, Ganie, & Wani, 2023).

Conclusions

The results of the XRD test showed that the Silver was oxidized by approximately 25% due to inappropriate laboratory conditions used. The results of the XRD test also showed that the grain size of the silver oxide nanoparticles is (19.6 nm) and that its crystal structure is of the cubic type. It also showed that the grain size of the lead nanoparticles ranges between (16.6 nm_17.4 nm). Its crystal structure is cubic.

A UV test was performed and peaks of absorbance, transmittance, and gap energy

appeared. It was proven that the materials that were prepared are materials within the nanoscale range.

Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) was used to determine the morphological characteristics of the nanoparticles. It was a form. The biosynthesized AgNps are spherical, with diameters ranging from (46 nm) to (82 nm) and falling within the nanoparticle boundaries. The shape of the biosynthesized PbNps was spherical and some particles were irregular in shape with diameters ranging from (99 nm) to (138 nm). In addition, a few aggregates were observed, and most of the nanoparticles appeared spherical in shape, and these results are consistent with what was obtained.

The nano-lead loaded on cumin seeds and the nano-silver loaded on the mint plant showed effectiveness in inhibition the bacteria (*Pseudomonas luteola*) taken by swab it from the contact lenses of the eye of a person carrying these bacteria. There was effectiveness in inhibition that bacteria, as the measurement of

the inhibition area was 23.48 mm with lead. Nanoparticles and 18.37mm silver nanoparticles.

According to the interpretation of the results and comparisons made, the effectiveness for inhibition of lead was greater, making it a pesticide and antibacterial suitable for use in medical and commercial fields and in sterilization.

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